

THE DESTINY OF A MAN - THE LIFE OF USMAN YUSUPOV

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Abstract. This article provides information about Usman Yusupov, who worked as the leader of Uzbekistan during the Second World War, the work he did during his life and administration, and his role in the history of our country.

Keywords: Second World War, Usman Yusupov, front, head of state, fascism, Communist Party, evacuation

Usman Yusupov is one of the leaders who played an important role in the history of Uzbekistan during the Soviet era. The years of his leadership of the republic were very controversial, not only in Uzbekistan, but also in the entire USSR. Of course, Usman Yusupov was a product of his time, the Soviet system. But his leadership and initiative, his ability to understand the pain of the people, the embodiment of patriotism and humanitarian aspects in one person allowed him to become a political person.

Usman Yusupov, a well-known state and political figure, an ardent son of the Uzbek people, was born on March 1, 1900, in the village of Kaptarkhana in the present-day Fergana district, in a poor peasant family. From 1916, he continued working as an ordinary worker at a cotton ginning factory in the present Yangiyol district. His political activity began in 1923. Later, he held the positions of chairman of the Tashkent Builders Association, chairman of the Tashkent District Council of Trade Unions (1923-1926), student of the course of Marxism-Leninism under the Central Committee of the VKP(b) (1934-36), People's Commissar of Food of the Uzbek SSR (1936-1937). [A2 B183]. After that, in 1937, he took the position of the first secretary of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan. This period coincided with the period of repressive policy carried out by the Soviet totalitarian regime. The repression of many state and party leaders created a sense of confusion and depression in the society. In such a difficult situation, Usman Yusupov was entrusted with difficult tasks.

When evaluating Usman Yusupov's political activity, it is necessary to pay attention to two aspects of the issue. First of all, during the years when Usman Yusupov worked as the head of the Republic, large water facilities were built in Uzbekistan at the expense of the people through his initiative. As a leader, he approved the initiative of the farmers and united the population to solve the water problem. In 1939, the completion of the 270-km-long Big Ferghana Canal in a very short period of time - 45 days, inspired the people and developed their

labor initiative [A1 B72]. In addition, the construction of the Kattakorgan reservoir, Rudasoy and Kosonsoy reservoirs, Farhod hydroelectric power station was the beginning of the construction of the largest gyrotechnical facilities of this period.

Usman Yusupov showed his qualities as a great politician and strong-willed leader even during the Second World War. It is known that in complex emergency situations, not only the will, moral and spiritual qualities of a person are tested, but also his idealism, faith, and sincerity. In the early years of the war, more than 250,000 children separated from their parents due to the war, 270 large factories, about 700 scientific institutions, higher education institutions, art groups were moved to Uzbekistan from a number of regions of Russia, Ukraine and Belarus. Reaction to these was a test for local leaders and residents [A5 B1]. It was not easy to find a production space for each enterprise in a short period of time, install equipment, and prepare products for the front. It has become more difficult to find shelter, work and create conditions for children, workers, scientific and technical personnel, figures of science, literature, art and their families who have been relocated from war-torn regions.

When these issues were discussed in the bureau of the Central Committee of the Communist Party of Uzbekistan, it was emphasized that all people are coming to the republic temporarily and they should be welcomed with hospitality. Only some people spoke about their lack of housing, food, and other limited opportunities. Then Usman Yusupov rejected such excuses, saying that it is necessary to show everyone's internationalism. Several commissions were formed to receive evacuees. The people of Uzbekistan warmly welcomed the visitors. They accepted them as their own, gave them shelter, food, and clothes.

All industrial enterprises in Uzbekistan were re-equipped to produce products for the needs of the front. Within a few months, the whole of Uzbekistan has been turned into a military region that supplies the front with everything from ordinary rifle bullets to military airplanes and parachutes. Food products, basic parts of clothes produced here were sent to military soldiers. The workers of Uzbekistan fulfilled their patriotic duty and contributed to the victory over the enemy. Naturally, these works were organized and led by the government of Uzbekistan under the leadership of Usman Yusupov.

Secondly, Usman Yusupov made some mistakes in his leadership activity. During the mass repressions in Uzbekistan in 1937-1939, he was forced to follow the orders of the Center. However, he wrote a letter to the head of state of the USSR and asked him to reduce the repressions. However, Usman Yusupov strongly

believed in the communist idea during his leadership career and worked with this ideology in his ideological views [A2 B184].

During his political career, Usman Yusupov tried to protect the interests of the people of Uzbekistan. For example, during the war years, in order to save the Uzbek people from famine, I.V. He was strongly criticized by Stalin.

The well-known state and political figure Nuriddin Muhiddinov recalls the following about the work of Usman Yusupov in his memoirs: "I also knew Usman Yusupov well. He will be the one to give me a referral to party work. We worked with him for a long time. Therefore, I consider it my duty as a human being to say a few words about his life and work. Usman Yusupov spoke to me for the first time in 1939 at a meeting of the Komsomol of Uzbekistan in Tashkent. He talked with regional leaders between meetings. At that time, I graduated from the trade institute in Moscow and worked as the deputy head of the personnel department of the Bukhara regional press association and the head of the educational complex.

Despite his mistakes and shortcomings, Usman Yusupov is a truly great man who honestly led our republic in the most difficult and difficult period of our history, spent all his efforts for the peace and well-being of the country, and left dozens of disciples behind him. was a human being. The life path of such people is considered a part of the history of their people and should be an example for our youth. Personally, I am proud to be a student of Usman and to work side by side with him.

Once, after returning from a long-term foreign business trip, I came to Tashkent and went to Khalqabad with Olmas. I visited the house-museum where Usman Yusupov lived with his family and looked at the exhibits. I wrote the following words in the memory notebook: "The bright memory of Usman Yusupov, a worthy son of the Uzbek people, a true communist, patriot, our elder brother and teacher, is always in our memory" [A5 B3].

Konstantin Simonov, the famous writer of Usman Yusupov's great deeds in the war, in his works, boxing champion of Uzbekistan and Central Asia, military intelligence officer, writer, author of the book "Generalissimus", which has been reprinted 3 times so far, Hero of the Soviet Union Vladimir Karpovlar which they recorded with special affection in their memories. Vladimir Karpov, the secretary of the Union of Writers of the USSR, who was awarded the title of Hero of the Soviet Union for his combat services in the war, recalls: "Usman Yusupov said this thought that I will remember throughout my life: "Dear Volodya. Know that this award you received, this star shining on your chest, will help you in your life. You grow up, you move forward in work and position [A3 B121].

In those difficult times, it was not so difficult for every political leader to discredit him with a provocation. Usman Yusupov was also accused of maliciousness and adventurism before the war, of treason and hiding enemies of the country during the war, and of repressions carried out before the war after the war. The case reached such a level that in 1946, as a result of an anonymous application, the "Yusupov case" was initiated. The members of the Politburo: V.M. Molotov, G.M. Malenkov and the secretary of the Central Committee N.S. Patolichev were engaged in this work and were engaged in the work of protecting his pure name.

Usman Yusupov, a great-hearted and skilled political figure, died in Tashkent on May 7, 1966. He was buried in the Chigatai cemetery in Tashkent. A marble bust is placed on his grave. Usman Yusupov published a 3-volume book on party building and issues. So, the work of the great figure of the Uzbek people is commendable. His home museum is operating in Yangiyol.

In particular, the character of each person determines the rate of his contemporaries. The famous Uzbek writer Gafur Ghulam said the following at the funeral of Usman Yusupov. During the Second World War, he showed enthusiasm in raising the patriotism of the people, organized the people's power to supply the front with the necessary weapons and products, participated in ensuring the strength of the rear of the front, showed kindness to those who lost their homes due to the war, took care of orphans. wiper Our benevolent Usman Yusupov especially loved art and literature and cared for each of the people of art and literature. In particular, we will never forget the kindness and love shown to us during the calm years during the war!" He uttered his words with the heart-shaking song "Greetings to you from the great Fergana channel!" Greetings from Farhad HPP! Greetings from Kattakurgan! Greetings to you from the people of Mirzachol!..." [A5 B7]

Sharof Rashidov said at the gathering in Usman Yusupov's yard in Yangiyol: "We are sitting in the garden created by Usman Yusupov himself. Wherever Usman Yusupov stepped, gardens, new lands, flower beds, and life appeared within his reach. He was a real gardener. He successfully completed the tasks he set before him and returned with victory. We are witnesses of this."

Usman Yusupov was an example of responsibility for every word he spoke. He seemed to be quoting from philosophical aphorisms in his speech. So, Usman Yusupov was one of the figures who led Uzbekistan in the most difficult times, when the mill of cynicism was spinning with all its might and pulling our compatriots to its trap like a dragon. In our opinion, it is necessary to objectively illuminate the life path of the great state and party figure of Uzbekistan Usman

Yusupov and use the example of the glorious life and struggle of this figure to educate our entire nation, especially our youth. It is appropriate to create artistic and dramatic works, movies about this person, to immortalize his name.

People make history. Many wise statesmen, reliable leaders of the masses of workers and peasants, heroes of labor, figures of science, art and literature have grown up among our people. Among the great sons of the Uzbek nation, Akmal Ikramov, Fayzulla Khojayev, Yoldosh ota Okhunbobayov, Hamza Hakimzoda, Hamrokul Tursunkulov, Habib Abdullayev, Hamid Olimzhon, Usman Yusupov is one of these greats.

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